

UTILIZATION OF CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING APPROACH FOR SPEAKING SKILLS OF NURSING STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY OF CABUYAO

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach on the speaking skills of fourth-year nursing students at the University of Cabuyao. Employing a quantitative quasi-experimental design, the research utilized pretest and posttest evaluations to assess performance. Fifty students were selected through purposive sampling, with twenty-five assigned to the experimental group and twenty-five to the control group. A researcher-developed speaking test, validated by experts, measured five domains of speaking: fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy, using a four-point rubric. Statistical tools including mean, standard deviation, independent t-test, and paired t-test were applied to analyze the data. Results indicated that the experimental group demonstrated significantly higher posttest scores ($\bar{x}=88.59$) compared to the control group ($\bar{x}=83.73$). Significant differences were observed in all speaking domains: fluency ($t=4.853$, $p<.001$), coherence ($t=3.861$, $p<.001$), pronunciation ($t=2.977$, $p<.005$), vocabulary ($t=4.305$, $p<.001$), and grammatical accuracy ($t=3.525$, $p<.005$). Furthermore, the experimental group showed marked improvement from pretest to posttest, while the control group exhibited minimal gains. These findings affirm the effectiveness of the CLIL approach in enhancing students' speaking abilities. As a practical output, a CLIL-based speaking activities handbook was proposed to aid nursing instructors in fostering language development through integrated content instruction.

Keywords: *Utilization, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) Approach, Speaking Skills*

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized healthcare landscape, effective communication in English is indispensable for nursing professionals, particularly in contexts requiring accurate patient interaction, interdisciplinary collaboration, and international practice. In the Philippines, English remains the primary medium of instruction in higher education, as mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2013). Despite this, many nursing students continue to face challenges in oral communication, particularly in fluency, coherence, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy—skills essential for clinical competence and professional growth (Salvador, 2022; Pretorius, 2020). These challenges are especially evident among fourth-year nursing students at the University of Cabuyao, who are required to take the general education course *The Contemporary World*, a subject that demands both critical thinking and effective verbal articulation of global issues.

To address these issues, the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach has emerged as a promising pedagogical innovation. CLIL integrates subject content with language instruction, enabling learners to develop both academic knowledge and communicative competence simultaneously (Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2020). International studies have demonstrated CLIL's effectiveness in improving students' speaking skills and subject comprehension (Cabrales Vega et al., 2021; Lyu, 2022). However, there remains a notable gap in localized, data-driven research on CLIL's application in non-language disciplines such as nursing, particularly within general education subjects like *The Contemporary World* (Rulona & Bacasmot, 2023). Moreover, most existing studies rely on qualitative methods, leaving a methodological gap in quantitative evaluations of CLIL's impact on speaking proficiency.

This study addresses these gaps by implementing a quasi-experimental design to evaluate the effectiveness of CLIL in enhancing the speaking skills of fourth-year nursing students at the University of Cabuyao, specifically within the context of *The Contemporary World* subject. It focuses on five key domains—fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy—using a validated rubric and the Oral Proficiency Interview (OPI) framework. By integrating CLIL into this general education course, the study not only responds to the urgent need for innovative language instruction in nursing education but also aligns with CHED's call for flexible, student-centered learning strategies (CHED, 2020). The study further proposes a CLIL-based speaking activities handbook to support educators in implementing content-integrated language instruction, thereby contributing to both academic research and practical pedagogy.

Research Questions

1. What is the pretest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the control group in speaking skills in terms of:
 - 1.1 Fluency,
 - 1.2 Coherence,
 - 1.3 Pronunciation,
 - 1.4 Vocabulary, and

- 1.5 Grammatical Accuracy?
2. What is the pretest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the experimental group in speaking skills in terms of:
 - 2.1 Fluency,
 - 2.2 Coherence,
 - 2.3 Pronunciation,
 - 2.4 Vocabulary, and
 - 2.5 Grammatical Accuracy?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?
4. What is the posttest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the control group in speaking skills in terms of:
 - 4.1 Fluency,
 - 4.2 Coherence,
 - 4.3 Pronunciation,
 - 4.4 Vocabulary, and
 - 4.5 Grammatical Accuracy?
5. What is the posttest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the experimental group in speaking skills in terms of:
 - 5.1 Fluency,
 - 5.2 Coherence,
 - 5.3 Pronunciation,
 - 5.4 Vocabulary, and
 - 5.5 Grammatical Accuracy?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control and experimental group?
8. Based on the findings of the study, what handbook may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at a local government-funded higher education institution in Cabuyao, Laguna, during the second semester of the academic year 2024–2025. The research focused on fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Nursing students enrolled in the general education course The Contemporary World. A quasi-experimental design was employed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach in enhancing students' speaking skills.

The study utilized purposive sampling to select 50 respondents—25 students each from two pre-existing sections. The experimental group received CLIL-based instruction, while the control group was taught using conventional methods. The sampling was stratified by gender and preliminary grade ranges to ensure academic comparability. Each group consisted of 18 female and 7 male students, with representation across four grade brackets (70.1–74.0, 78.1–82.0, 82.1–86.0, and 86.1–90.0).

Data were gathered through pretest and posttest assessments using a researcher-made speaking test instrument. The instrument was structured around the Oral Proficiency Interview (OPI) framework and consisted of six questions divided into four stages: Warm-Up, Level Check, Probing, and Wind-Down. Each response was evaluated using a 4-point rubric (Very Good, Good, Fair, Poor) across five domains: fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy. The rubric was validated by five experts, including graduate school professors and language specialists, and achieved a Content Validity Index (CVI) of 1.00, indicating strong content validity. Pilot testing was not conducted due to the quasi-experimental nature of the study.

The data gathering process involved synchronous and asynchronous methods. Pretests were conducted via Google Meet and recorded for evaluation. Posttests were administered through voice recordings. All responses were independently rated by two trained interraters to ensure objectivity and reliability.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics included mean and standard deviation to summarize performance across speaking domains. Inferential statistics involved paired t-tests to compare pretest and posttest scores within groups, and independent t-tests to assess differences between the control and experimental groups. A significance level of 0.05 was used to determine statistical significance.

The study was limited to fourth-year nursing students enrolled in a single general education subject at one institution, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. It focused exclusively on speaking skills and did not assess other language domains such as reading, writing, or listening. The intervention period was limited to four weeks, which may not capture long-term effects of the CLIL approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the pretest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the control group in speaking skills in terms of:

1.1 Fluency

Table 1.1

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	5	27.78
Intermediate	12	66.67
Basic	1	5.56
Beginner	0	0

Total	18	100.00
Average	83.61	
SD	2.70	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate		
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner		

The **fluency** scores averaged **83.61** with a standard deviation of **2.70**. Most students (66.67%) were rated *Intermediate*, showing minimal pauses and generally smooth responses. Five students (27.78%) were rated *Advanced*, speaking with promptness and natural flow, while one student (5.56%) was rated *Basic* due to frequent hesitation. No student attained the Proficient level, indicating limited ability in spontaneous, extended speech.

Based on the speaking rubric and oral proficiency interview stages, this result implies that while the students can handle introductory or warm-up questions such as self-introductions and basic descriptions about globalization, they tend to struggle with Probing Stage questions that require critical reflection and extended argumentation. Their fluency tends to falter during more cognitively demanding responses, such as defending a viewpoint on migration or aging populations.

This outcome was echoed in the findings of Rahimi and Fathi (2022), who argued that speaking fluency is developed through regular and meaningful interaction, a feature often missing in traditional classrooms. Salvador (2022) also observed that lecture-based approaches in Philippine higher education tended to emphasize written tasks, leaving speaking skills underdeveloped.

1.2 Coherence

Table 1.2

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Coherence

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	2	11.11
Intermediate	11	61.11
Basic	5	27.78
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	81.11	
SD	2.74	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate		
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner		

The **coherence** had an average score of **81.11** with a standard deviation of **2.74**. Eleven students (61.11%) were rated *Intermediate*, two (11.11%) *Advanced*, and five

(27.78%) *Basic*. This indicated that most students presented ideas with some structure but struggled with logical flow and clarity.

Difficulties are evident in responding to questions that required cause-effect reasoning or defending a claim, particularly during the Probing and Level Check Stages, where higher-order thinking and cohesive expression were needed. This pattern highlights the students' limited ability to organize and connect ideas during speaking activities. Despite having content knowledge, they frequently lack the transitional language and rhetorical control necessary to present their responses as cohesive wholes. As per the rubric, students at this level may convey ideas with occasional lapses in structure, making their message harder to follow. This further reflects a lack of exposure to structured oral discourse tasks, such as panel discussions, oral defense, or debate activities—essential for fostering coherence, particularly in a content-heavy subject like *The Contemporary World*.

This pattern aligned with the study of Khasawneh (2023), who emphasized that coherence is strengthened through repeated exposure to structured speaking tasks such as problem-solving and presentations. Similarly, Rulona and Bacasmot (2023) found that traditional Philippine classrooms often neglected the organization of ideas in oral responses, focusing instead on content recall. These findings affirmed that the limited coherence among students may have stemmed from insufficient emphasis on spoken argumentation—a gap that CLIL aimed to bridge through integrated content-based speaking.

1.3 Pronunciation

Table 1.3

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Pronunciation

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	5	0
Advanced	4	22.22
Intermediate	9	50.00
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	86.17	
SD	4.10	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

Pronunciation was the highest-performing area for the control group, with an average score of **86.17** and a standard deviation of **4.10**. Half of the students (50%) were rated *Intermediate*, while four (22.22%) were *Advanced*, and the remaining five (27.78%) received a *Proficient* rating. No students fell under the Fair or Poor categories.

This indicates a relatively strong foundation in pronunciation, possibly developed through repetition and passive exposure such as reading aloud, listening to lectures, and teacher modeling. However, the quality of pronunciation may be superficial, as students tend to struggle with new or content-specific terms in Probing Stage responses. While the rubric highlights accuracy in articulation and appropriate stress as indicators of higher-level performance, students may not consistently apply these features in spontaneous speech. Therefore, pronunciation in the control group appears to reflect mechanical reproduction, not adaptive use in varied speech contexts.

A similar trend was observed in the study of Ningsih (2024), who noted that pronunciation is often enhanced by listening and mimicry, even in the absence of interactive speaking tasks. This observation was supported by Tatlı et al. (2022), who warned that high pronunciation scores may mask underlying weaknesses in spontaneous oral delivery. Additionally, Zhussupova and Shadiev (2023) highlighted the value of cultural and content-rich discussions for sustaining pronunciation gains—elements which CLIL incorporates but traditional instruction typically does not.

1.4 Vocabulary

Table 1.4

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Vocabulary

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	13	72.22
Intermediate	4	22.22
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	81.11	
SD	2.08	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The **vocabulary** got an average score of **81.11** with a standard deviation of **2.08**. 72.22% of students were rated *Advanced*, 22.22% *Intermediate*, and 5.56% *Proficient*.

Although students appear confident in using commonly used terms, many responses lack discipline-specific language, especially in Probing and Wind-down Stages. This restricts their ability to articulate complex or abstract concepts, particularly those relevant to nursing or global citizenship.

This finding resonated with the work of Daidone and Darcy (2021), who argued that students need academic and domain-specific vocabulary to clearly express complex ideas, especially in content-based subjects. Moreover, Çelik and Ersanlı (2022) emphasized that CLIL instruction broadens students’ vocabulary range by immersing

them in authentic, context-driven language use. These insights help explain why students in the control group, taught using conventional methods, demonstrated strong general vocabulary but limited academic or content-specific lexicon.

1.5 Grammatical Accuracy

Table 1.5

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Grammatical Accuracy

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	6	33.33
Intermediate	9	50.00
Basic	3	16.67
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	82.33	
SD	3.16	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

Grammatical **accuracy** attained an average score of **82.33** with a standard deviation of **3.16**. Half of the students (50%) were rated *Intermediate*, 33.33% *Advanced*, and 16.67% *Basic*.

This suggests a command of grammar at the sentence level, but reduced flexibility in real-time applications. The lack of integrated speaking practice, where grammar is applied in context, limits students' ability to construct longer, complex responses with consistent accuracy.

Similar conclusions were drawn by Zou et al. (2023), who found that grammatical accuracy improves significantly when learners are engaged in meaningful speaking tasks where they must apply grammar in real-time contexts. Likewise, Lu et al. (2023) reported that CLIL enhances grammar competence by embedding functional structures in academic content. These studies support the observation that while the control group shows grammatical awareness, their skills remain largely mechanical due to limited contextual speaking practice.

Research Question 2. What is the pretest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the experimental group in speaking skills in terms of:

2.1 Fluency

Table 2.1

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	4	22.22
Intermediate	10	55.56
Basic	3	16.67
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	82.78	
SD	2.58	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

An average **fluency** score of **82.78** was recorded with a standard deviation of **2.58**. Most students (55.56%) were rated *Intermediate*, 22.22% *Advanced*, 16.67% *Basic*, and 5.56% *Proficient*.

It is observed that students have the capacity to deliver verbal responses but lack the ease and flow that characterize strong fluency. They often pause mid-sentence or restart ideas, indicating a need for guided practice in maintaining uninterrupted speech. Their responses during the Probing Stage—especially when asked questions requiring extended thought often reflect hesitancy and limited spontaneous output.

Evidence of this challenge in traditional instruction was emphasized by Jefferson et al. (2020), who found that fluency improved significantly when students were immersed in content-rich speaking tasks. Likewise, Salvador (2022) highlighted that conventional methods often failed to provide structured opportunities for oral production, which led to stagnation in speaking development. These findings supported the idea that fluency requires sustained, meaningful communication—one of the central strategies offered through CLIL.

2.2 Coherence

Table 2.2

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Coherence

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	2	11.11
Intermediate	10	55.56
Basic	5	27.78
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	82.33	
SD	3.74	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **coherence** score was **82.33** with a standard deviation of **3.74**. Over half of the students (55.56%) were rated *Intermediate*, 27.78% *Basic*, 11.11% *Advanced*, and one student (5.56%) *Proficient*.

Coherence appears to be one of the areas most in need of improvement. Students can generate ideas but often fail to arrange them coherently. Their responses during analytical or opinion-based questions tend to shift abruptly or include loosely connected ideas. This aligns with the rubric's description for "Intermediate" and "Fair" performance. CLIL supports coherence development through scaffolded speaking tasks that require logical sequencing, especially when learners engage with interdisciplinary content.

This observation echoed the study of Rahmawati et al. (2023), who found that coherence improved when learners were given tasks centered on real-world, meaningful topics. Additionally, Hui and Md (2023) reported that students engaged in CLIL-style discussions developed stronger sequencing skills and transitions in speech, reinforcing the importance of contextualized language use for coherent expression.

2.3 Pronunciation

Table 2.3

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Pronunciation

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	8	44.44
Intermediate	9	50.00

Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	84.94	
SD	2.86	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate		
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner		

The average **pronunciation** score was 84.94 with a standard deviation of 2.86. Half of the students (50%) were rated Intermediate, 44.44% Advanced, and 5.56% Proficient, with no students falling below Intermediate.

It is observed that while students generally articulate English sounds well, they tend to struggle with less familiar vocabulary, especially during more complex discussions. The rubric for “Advanced” pronunciation emphasizes accurate stress, rhythm, and intelligibility—all of which students demonstrate at times but not consistently across all speaking tasks.

A similar pattern was noted by Zhussupova and Shadiev (2023), who found that pronunciation skills progressed more rapidly when students spoke in content-embedded, culturally relevant settings. In the same vein, Ningsih (2024) emphasized that repeated oral use of academic language enhanced clarity and accuracy in articulation. The findings of Bonner et al. (2023) further reinforced that student in technical disciplines, such as nursing, benefited from content-driven speaking tasks in improving pronunciation of complex terms.

2.4 Vocabulary

Table 2.4

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Vocabulary

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	3	16.67
Intermediate	12	66.67
Basic	3	16.67
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	81.67	
SD	2.30	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate		
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner		

The average **vocabulary** score was **81.67** with a standard deviation of **2.30**. Most students (66.67%) were rated *Intermediate*, while 16.67% were rated *Advanced* and another 16.67% *Basic*. No students reached Proficient.

This vocabulary performance reflects a dependence on common or general-purpose words. Students can respond, but they often avoid or misuse terms that would make their communication more academic or specific. The rubric for higher scores requires broader vocabulary and subject-relevant terms, which are limited here.

Findings by Çelik and Ersanlı (2022) demonstrated that vocabulary acquisition became more effective when terms were taught and applied within academic content. Moreover, Salvador (2022) pointed out that traditional methods did not offer sufficient exposure to discipline-specific language, whereas CLIL environments promoted better vocabulary retention and application through real-world engagement.

Table 2.5

Pretest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Grammatical Accuracy

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	4	22.22
Intermediate	9	50.00
Basic	5	27.78
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	81.94	
SD	3.19	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **grammatical accuracy** score of the experimental group was **81.94** with a standard deviation of **3.19**. Nine students (50%) were scored *Intermediate*, four (22.22%) *Advanced*, and five (27.78%) *Basic*. No students reached Proficient or scored below the Basic level.

Grammatical usage among the experimental group appears functional but limited. Students apply rules correctly in simple responses, but they often lose accuracy when speaking spontaneously or when expressing nuanced ideas. This aligns with rubric indicators for mechanical or inconsistent control.

As found by Hu et al. (2023), grammatical accuracy significantly improves when students are tasked with using grammar to convey content, rather than reciting rules. Zou et al. (2023) similarly report that integrated and immediate feedback during speaking tasks helps learners apply grammar in more flexible, accurate ways.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 3

Test Significant Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Nursing Students in the Control and Experimental Groups in Speaking Skills

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Pretest	.065	.948	Not Significant	Accept H01

There was no significant difference in assessment of the control and experimental groups in speaking skills. The computed p-value was **.948**, which **was greater than the 0.05** level of significance, indicating *no statistically significant difference between the two groups* prior to the intervention. As a result, the *null hypothesis was accepted*.

This result indicates that both groups share an equal footing in terms of speaking skill development at the beginning of the study. Their comparable ratings in the rubric-based categories such as fluency (“with minimal hesitation”), coherence (“some logical structure”), and grammatical accuracy (“mostly correct basic structures”) suggest that neither group has an instructional or linguistic advantage prior to the intervention.

This result echoed the findings of Rahimi and Fathi (2022), who emphasized that establishing baseline equivalence between groups is essential for evaluating instructional interventions in language learning. This affirmed the importance of a statistically equal starting point when assessing the effectiveness of content-integrated speaking strategies.

Research Question 4. What is the posttest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the control group in speaking skills in terms of:

4.1 Fluency

Table 4.1

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	8	44.44
Intermediate	9	50.00
Basic	0	
Beginner	0	
Total	18	100.00
Average	84.17	

SD	2.50	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient	85- 89 Advanced	80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic	74 Below Beginner	

The average **fluency** score was **84.17** with a standard deviation of **2.50**, showing a *modest increase* from the pretest average of **83.61**. Half of the students (50%) remained in the *Intermediate* rating, 44.44% improved to *Advanced*, and one student (5.56%) reached *Proficient*. No student scored below Intermediate, indicating slight overall improvement.

The minimal gain in fluency among the control group suggests that traditional instruction alone may not be enough to promote fluid and confident speaking. The lack of engaging, content-based speaking activities limits the students' opportunities to practice sustained oral communication.

As indicated by Salvador (2022), classrooms dominated by teacher-talk offer limited chances for learners to build fluency in spontaneous discourse. Khasawneh (2023) also found that without real-time and task-based speaking practice, fluency gains tend to be incremental and uneven. The control group's stagnant performance echoed these findings, showing how exposure alone does not guarantee fluidity in spoken output.

4.2 Coherence

Table 4.2

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Coherence

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	1	5.56
Intermediate	6	33.33
Basic	11	61.11
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	80.11	
SD	3.10	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient	85- 89 Advanced	80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic	74 Below Beginner	

The average **coherence** score was **80.11** with a standard deviation of **3.10**, reflecting a slight decrease from the pretest score of **81.11**. A majority of students (61.11%) were rated *Basic*, 33.33% *Intermediate*, and only one student (5.56%) reached *Advanced*.

The decline in coherence is significant because it demonstrates that content mastery alone does not translate into effective spoken communication. Students may

4.4 Vocabulary

Table 4.4

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Vocabulary

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	1	5.56
Intermediate	11	61.11
Basic	6	33.33
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	80.33	
SD	2.22	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **vocabulary** score for the control group was **80.33** with a standard deviation of **2.22**. 61.11% of students were rated *Intermediate*, 33.33% *Basic*, and one student (5.56%) reached *Advanced*. This represented a *slight decline* from the pretest average of **81.11**

While students may recognize terms presented in class, they lack the opportunity to apply them in real-time speaking. This limits their ability to construct responses beyond surface-level communication. Vocabulary acquisition requires not just exposure, but active use—which was not fully supported by traditional instruction.

Findings by Çelik and Ersanlı (2022) revealed that vocabulary acquisition was significantly stronger when students were required to use new words in contextualized speaking activities. Similarly, Salvador (2022) emphasized that without active engagement, vocabulary knowledge remained passive. The performance of the control group clearly reflected this limitation.

4.5 Grammatical Accuracy

Table 4.5

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Control Group in terms of Grammatical Accuracy

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	5	27.78
Intermediate	10	55.56
Basic	3	16.67

Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	82.28	
SD	2.93	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient	85- 89 Advanced	80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic	74 Below Beginner	

The average **grammatical accuracy** score was **82.28** with a standard deviation of **2.93**. This was a *slight decrease* from the pretest score of **82.33**. More than half of the students (55.56%) were rated *Intermediate*, 27.78% *Advanced*, and 16.67% *Basic*.

The grammatical accuracy remains static because students did not have the opportunity to apply rules in practical, spoken scenarios. Grammar is often limited to written drills or multiple-choice exercises and not practiced through spontaneous speaking.

Zou et al. (2023) noted that grammatical development occurs more reliably when learners use language in real-time communication rather than decontextualized drills. Likewise, Hu et al. (2023) found that accuracy improves when grammar is applied in speaking tasks rather than isolated worksheets. These studies align with the control group’s stagnant performance, highlighting the limitations of traditional instruction in developing functional grammar skills.

Research Question 5. What is the posttest score of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students in the experimental group in speaking skills in terms of:

5.1 Fluency

Table 5.1

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	3	16.67
Advanced	10	55.56
Intermediate	5	27.78
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	86.39	
SD	3.48	
Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient	85- 89 Advanced	80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic	74 Below Beginner	

The average **fluency** score was **86.39** with a standard deviation of **3.48**, showing a *strong improvement* from the pretest average of **82.78**. Many students (55.56%) were rated *Advanced*, 27.78% *Intermediate*, and 16.67% *Proficient*. No students were rated below *Intermediate*, indicating consistent proficiency across the group.

This improvement in fluency suggests that integrating language learning with Contemporary World content allows students to speak more confidently and spontaneously. Through repeated practice, students achieve a more natural flow, as required by the upper tiers of the fluency rubric.

As highlighted by Jefferson et al. (2020), fluency notably increases when students use language to navigate content-driven discussions. Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) also found that CLIL creates interactive spaces where learners are required to speak regularly, which directly supports fluency development. Furthermore, Salvador (2022) observed that CLIL breaks down teacher-centered dominance and gives learners more opportunities to talk, thus enhancing spontaneous speech.

5.2 Coherence

Table 5.2

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Coherence

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	1	5.56
Advanced	6	33.33
Intermediate	11	61.11
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	84.28	
SD	2.54	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **coherence** score was **84.28** with a standard deviation of **2.54**, showing a *visible improvement* from the pretest average of **82.33**. Most students (61.11%) were rated *Intermediate*, 33.33% *Advanced*, and 5.56% *Proficient*.

The improvement in coherence is a direct result of CLIL's structured approach to combining academic content with communication. As nursing students, the capacity to organize information clearly is vital, and CLIL scaffolds such communication effectively by requiring coherent speech during classroom discussions and assessments.

In support of this, Rahmawati et al. (2023) showed that linking language with real-world content enhances learners' ability to construct logical, well-connected speech. Hui

and Md (2023) further demonstrated that task-based learning, as seen in CLIL, fosters coherence by training students to speak with purpose and structure. Similarly, Salvador (2022) confirmed that CLIL discussions create intentional communication scenarios where coherence naturally develops through repeated academic use.

5.3 Pronunciation

Table 5.3

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Pronunciation

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	10	55.56
Advanced	6	33.33
Intermediate	2	11.11
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	89.44	
SD	3.79	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

Pronunciation was the highest performing indicator, with an average score of **89.44** and a standard deviation of **3.79**. Over half of the students (55.56%) achieved a *Proficient* rating, 33.33% were *Advanced*, and 11.11% were *Intermediate*. No student scored below *Intermediate*, demonstrating a *remarkable improvement* from the pretest score of **84.94**.

According to the rubric, Proficient in pronunciation is characterized by clear articulation, correct stress, and intonation that enhance understanding. These qualities are most apparent during students' use of academic terms across all stages of the speaking tasks. It is evident that students enhanced not only their accuracy in word pronunciation but also their rhythm and prosody during discussion. The CLIL model ensures frequent practice with content-specific vocabulary like “secularization” or “diaspora,” which naturally requires correct pronunciation in context. Rather than practicing isolated drills, students rehearse pronunciation through real use, which matches rubric expectations for intelligibility and appropriate stress in natural speech.

Building on this, Zhussupova and Shadiev (2023) found that pronunciation developed best in immersive, content-based speaking environments—like CLIL classrooms. These environments naturally integrated language learning with subject matter instruction, allowing learners to practice pronunciation in meaningful, communicative contexts. Ningsih (2024) found that technology-assisted CLIL programs improved pronunciation by focusing on repeated exposure within academic contexts, where learners encountered and produced target language sounds in varied and

purposeful ways. Bonner et al. (2023) also reported gains in pronunciation accuracy and confidence in CLIL-supported virtual simulations, affirming the value of integrated instruction in achieving high-level articulation through realistic, interactive learning experiences.

5.4 Vocabulary

Table 5.4

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Vocabulary

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	2	11.11
Advanced	7	38.89
Intermediate	8	44.44
Basic	1	5.56
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	84.89	
SD	3.41	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **vocabulary** was **84.89** with a standard deviation of **3.41**. 44.44% of students were rated *Intermediate*, 38.89% *Advanced*, 11.11% *Proficient*, and one student (5.56%) was rated *Basic*. This marks *meaningful progress* compared to the pretest score of **81.67**.

The vocabulary growth in the experimental group illustrates the effectiveness of CLIL in promoting applied language learning. Students do not simply memorize vocabulary; they use it meaningfully when analyzing topics or forming arguments. The rubric emphasizes range and precision, both of which improve due to the repeated exposure and usage embedded in CLIL. This enhances their ability to discuss complex concepts with greater specificity, a vital skill in both academic discourse and future professional communication.

The findings align with Çelik and Ersanlı (2022), who stressed that vocabulary acquisition flourishes when language is taught within content-based lessons. Salvador (2022) also highlighted how peer interaction in CLIL contexts reinforces new terms and promotes retention. Further, Cubero (2023) showed that exposure to intercultural topics within CLIL environments increases vocabulary accuracy and contextual usage—matching what was observed in this study.

5.5 Grammatical Accuracy

Table 5.5

Posttest Score of the Nursing Students in the Experimental Group in terms of Grammatical Accuracy

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	6	33.33
Advanced	4	22.22
Intermediate	7	38.89
Basic	1	5.56
Beginner	0	0
Total	18	100.00
Average	86.00	
SD	4.37	

Legend: 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate
 75 - 79 Basic 74 Below Beginner

The average **grammatical accuracy** score was **86.00** with a standard deviation of **4.37**, which was *significantly higher* than the pretest average of **81.94**. 38.89% of students were rated *Intermediate*, 22.22% *Advanced*, 33.33% *Proficient*, and one student (5.56%) was rated *Basic*.

According to the rubric, Proficient speakers construct grammatically sound sentences using a variety of structures with minimal error. This improvement was particularly evident in complex spoken responses during the Probing Stage, where students produced longer and more accurate utterances. The students are no longer limited to basic sentence structures. They began applying more complex grammar—such as modals, conditionals, and reported speech—within their spontaneous communication. CLIL lessons do not teach grammar in isolation; rather, students are expected to use it to discuss academic ideas. This integration reinforces rule retention and functional accuracy. By linking grammar with communication, CLIL turns passive grammar knowledge into active speech tools, aligning with rubric descriptors for advanced performance.

These results align with findings by Zou et al. (2023), who reported that grammatical accuracy improves when learners receive real-time feedback during content-rich discussions. Hu et al. (2023) similarly found that CLIL contexts lead to long-term grammar gains through repeated, functional use. Vo et al. (2023) highlighted the role of authentic academic language tasks in developing both accuracy and complexity. This mirrors the results seen here, where grammar proficiency is enhanced by the meaningful, sustained communication fostered by CLIL.

Research Question 6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 6

Test of Significant Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Nursing Students in the Control and Experimental Groups

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Posttest	-3.906	.000	Significant	Reject Ho2

There was a statistically significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups in speaking skills. The **p-value of .000** was *lower than* the **.05 level of significance**, leading to the **rejection of the null hypothesis**. This confirmed that *the experimental group outperformed the control group in the posttest*.

This significant difference highlights the value of CLIL in fostering real communication skills within academic settings. Students in the experimental group engage with Contemporary World content not only for subject learning but also as a tool for active language development. Through CLIL, they are consistently exposed to content-integrated speaking tasks across all speaking assessment stages—from the Warm-up and Level Check to the more demanding Probing Stage. These tasks encourage them to use academic language meaningfully, develop structured responses, and articulate ideas clearly and confidently—all of which are emphasized in the rubric for higher speaking proficiency. The contrast in scores validates that students learn to speak better when language is used as a medium for expressing complex, subject-based ideas—something CLIL makes possible.

These findings are reinforced by Rahimi and Fathi (2022), who demonstrated that CLIL enhances speaking skills by integrating language use within academic tasks. Hu et al. (2023) further established that grammar and vocabulary improved more significantly in CLIL environments, where communication was authentic and purposeful. Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) also highlighted that learners in CLIL classrooms develop greater confidence and fluency due to constant use of language in real-life and academic scenarios. These studies support the current outcome—proving that CLIL is not only effective in theory but produces statistically significant gains in student speaking performance.

Research Question 7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control and experimental group?

Table 7

Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Nursing Students in the Control and Experimental Groups

Indicators	Paired Differences of the Pretest and Posttest of the Control Group				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	t	P value		
Control Fluency	-.556	1.580	-1.492	.154	Not Significant	Accept ho
Control Coherence	1.000	2.786	1.523	.146	Not Significant	Accept ho
Control Pronunciation	-1.000	2.196	-1.932	.070	Not Significant	Accept ho
Control Vocabulary	.778	1.801	1.833	.084	Not Significant	Accept ho
Control Grammatical	.0561	1.954	.121	.905	Not Significant	Accept ho
Experimental Fluency	-4.056	2.436	-7.061	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Experimental Coherence	-2.333	2.249	-4.401	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Experimental Pronunciation	-4.500	3.329	-5.733	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Experimental Vocabulary	-3.222	3.098	-4.413	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Experimental Grammatical	-4.056	3.403	-5.055	.000	Significant	Reject ho

For the **control group**, the results indicate **no significant improvements** in any of the speaking skill indicators. Specifically, fluency had a mean difference of -0.556 (SD = 1.580, $t = -1.492$, $p = .154$), coherence had a mean difference of 1.000 (SD = 2.786, $t = 1.523$, $p = .146$), pronunciation had a mean difference of -1.000 (SD = 2.196, $t = -1.932$, $p = .070$), vocabulary had a mean difference of 0.778 (SD = 1.801, $t = 1.833$, $p = .084$), and grammatical accuracy had a mean difference of 0.0561 (SD = 1.954, $t = 0.121$, $p = .905$).

In contrast, the **experimental group** showed **significant improvements** across all indicators, demonstrating the effectiveness of the CLIL approach in enhancing speaking skills. Fluency had a mean difference of -4.056 (SD = 2.436, $t = -7.061$, $p = .000$), coherence had a mean difference of -2.333 (SD = 2.249, $t = -4.401$, $p = .000$), pronunciation had a mean difference of -4.500 (SD = 3.329, $t = -5.733$, $p = .000$), vocabulary had a mean difference of -3.222 (SD = 3.098, $t = -4.413$, $p = .000$), and grammatical accuracy had a mean difference of -4.056 (SD = 3.403, $t = -5.055$, $p = .000$).

The null hypothesis (H0) for the control group, which states that there is no significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores, was accepted for all indicators. Conversely, the null hypothesis (H0) for the experimental group was rejected for all indicators, confirming the effectiveness of the CLIL approach.

These results suggest that traditional instructional methods were insufficient for enhancing these skills. These also align with several studies, weaving a comprehensive narrative of the effectiveness of the CLIL approach. Zou et al. (2023) reported that grammatical accuracy improved when learners received real-time feedback during content-rich discussions, which the CLIL approach provides. Building on this, Hu et al. (2023) found that CLIL contexts led to long-term grammar gains through repeated, functional use, reinforcing the benefits of integrating language learning with subject content. Vo et al. (2023) highlighted the role of authentic academic language tasks in developing both accuracy and complexity, aligning with the CLIL approach's emphasis on using language to discuss academic ideas. Salvador (2022) emphasized that traditional lecture-based approaches often fail to develop speaking skills effectively, corroborating the lack of significant improvement in the control group. Rahimi and Fathi (2022) demonstrated that CLIL enhances speaking skills by immersing students in content-based communication, reflecting the significant gains in the experimental group. Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) found that CLIL increases learner engagement and confidence by requiring consistent verbal participation in subject-based tasks, supporting the improved performance across all speaking skill indicators in the experimental group. In conclusion, the significant improvements observed in the experimental group validate the effectiveness of the CLIL approach in enhancing speaking skills, making it a valuable instructional strategy for language education.

Research Question 8. Based on the findings of the study, what handbook may be proposed?

The findings of this study highlight the need for structured guidance in implementing Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) methodologies within classroom settings. To address this need, a speaking activities handbook has been developed by the researcher. This research-made output is designed to provide educators with practical tools and activities that enhance both speaking skills and subject matter comprehension among students.

Conclusions

1. That traditional teaching methods are not sufficient to develop advanced speaking skills required for extended responses and critical reflection. In the broader context, this highlights the need for innovative instructional strategies to enhance speaking skills in educational settings.
2. That the pretest scores of the experimental group, which were like those of the control group, validate the study's design and ensure a fair basis for comparison. This comparability confirms that any observed improvements in the experimental group can be attributed to the CLIL approach rather than pre-existing differences

- in skill levels. This is significant as it establishes the reliability of the study and supports the use of CLIL as an effective approach.
3. That lack of significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups ensures that the improvements observed in the experimental group are due to the CLIL utilization. This reinforces the reliability of the study's results and the validity of the CLIL approach. It suggests that CLIL can be a powerful tool for enhancing speaking skills, providing a solid foundation for future research and implementation.
 4. That minimal improvement in the posttest scores of the control group highlights the limitations of traditional instructional methods in significantly enhancing speaking skills. This indicates that conventional teaching approaches are not effectively address the complexities of speaking skills. In the bigger picture, this calls for a reevaluation of traditional teaching methods and encourages the adoption of more interactive and content-based approaches.
 5. That significant improvement in the posttest scores of the experimental group demonstrates the effectiveness of the CLIL approach in enhancing speaking skills. Integrating language learning with content can lead to substantial gains in fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy. Reflectively, this suggests that CLIL can be a transformative approach in language education, fostering better communication skills and confidence among students.
 6. That the statistically significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups, with the experimental group outperforming the control group, confirms the effectiveness of the CLIL approach. Analytically, this supports the superiority of CLIL over traditional methods and highlights its potential for widespread adoption in educational practices.
 7. That the lack of statistically significant improvement in speaking skills of the control group, contrasted with the significant gains across all indicators in the experimental group, confirms the superiority of the CLIL approach over traditional methods. This suggests that CLIL can be effectively implemented across diverse educational contexts to enhance speaking skills.
 8. That the proposal of a comprehensive handbook incorporating CLIL methodologies into speaking activities may provide a valuable resource for educators. This handbook may offer practical tools to enhance speaking skills and subject matter comprehension, aligned with contemporary global issues, thereby fostering critical thinking, communication skills, and global awareness among students. In the broader context, this output may serve as a model for integrating CLIL into various educational programs, promoting a holistic approach to language learning.

Recommendations

1. Considering the average pretest performance of the control group, educational institutions are encouraged to develop and implement instructional strategies that target higher order speaking tasks. These strategies emphasize critical thinking, extended discourse, and the ability to articulate complex ideas—skills essential for academic and professional communication.

2. Given the similar pretest performance of both the control and experimental groups, future studies may prioritize baseline equivalence when assessing the effectiveness of instructional methods. Doing so ensures the validity of comparative outcomes and reinforces the credibility of results, especially when evaluating innovative approaches like CLIL.
3. To ensure that improvements in student performance are attributed solely to instructional interventions, educators and researchers may employ consistent and standardized pre-assessment protocols. This practice enhances the reliability of findings and supports data-driven decision-making in curriculum planning.
4. With the minimal improvement observed in the control group's posttest scores, school administrators and curriculum planners are urged to critically review the efficacy of traditional instructional approaches. Incorporating more dynamic, student-centered, and content-integrated methods may lead to better engagement and improved speaking outcomes.
5. The experimental group demonstrated significant gains across all indicators of speaking skills, the CLIL approach may be adopted in English language instruction, especially in content-heavy subjects such as Contemporary World. This integration supports both language development and subject comprehension, offering a holistic learning experience.
6. The statistically significant difference in posttest scores between the control and experimental groups supports the broader implementation of the CLIL approach. Educational institutions and policy makers are encouraged to integrate CLIL into mainstream curricula, recognizing its potential to enhance communication skills and academic performance simultaneously.
7. Given the superiority of the CLIL approach over traditional methods, educators may use CLIL as the primary framework in developing speaking modules. Its effectiveness across all evaluated indicators—fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy—makes it a valuable tool in language education.
8. The proposed CLIL-based handbook may be reviewed, validated, and officially adopted as a supplementary material in speaking instruction. It contains practical, content-integrated activities aligned with real-world themes that can enhance both speaking skills and content mastery among students.
9. Researchers and curriculum may replicate and adapt the CLIL handbook for use in nursing students specifically the fourth-year level. This can promote the sustainable application of CLIL across diverse educational contexts, ensuring its benefits reach a broader range of learners.

The Word of Worlds: The Contemporary World Handbook

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THE WORD OF WORLDS

WELCOME

Welcome to The Word of Worlds: The Contemporary World Handbook.

This handbook is designed to help educators integrate the content and language integrated learning (CLIL) approach into their teaching of the Contemporary World for high-achieving students. You'll find a variety of speaking activities aligned with the outcome-based teaching and learning (OBT&L) model to enhance students' understanding of globalization while improving their speaking skills. These activities foster critical thinking, effective communication, and a deeper understanding of global issues, empowering students to become positive communicators and informed global citizens.

Thank you for your dedication to enriching your students' learning experience and helping our students to see their vision to make a difference.

"The future belongs to those who believe in the beauty of their dreams."
— Eleanor Roosevelt

THE WORD OF WORLDS OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this handbook are to:

- Develop Communication Skills:** Improve students' speaking skills through structured activities that promote effective communication, critical thinking, and active participation.
- Foster Critical Thinking:** Encourage students to analyze and discuss global issues critically, creating their own informed opinions and solutions.
- Promote Global Citizenship:** Instill a sense of global citizenship and ethical responsibility, preparing students to engage with global challenges in their professional and personal lives.
- Support Professional Development:** Equip future students with the skills needed to navigate and address global health challenges, enhancing their professional competence and readiness for the globalized healthcare environment.

SPEAKING SKILLS RUBRIC

To ensure a consistent and fair evaluation of students' speaking skills throughout the course, we will use a standardized rubric for all speaking activities. This rubric is designed to assess key aspects of effective communication, including fluency, coherence, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical diversity. By providing clear criteria for both teachers and students, this rubric helps students understand the expectations and areas for improvement.

Criteria	Excellent	Good	Fair	Needs Improvement
Fluency	Speaks fluently and effortlessly, with minimal hesitation or filler words.	Speaks fluently, with occasional hesitation or filler words.	Speaks with some hesitation and frequent use of filler words.	Speaks with significant hesitation and frequent use of filler words.
Coherence	Ideas are presented in a clear, logical sequence, and the speaker maintains a strong focus on the topic.	Ideas are presented in a clear sequence, and the speaker maintains focus on the topic.	Ideas are somewhat clear but may lack a strong focus on the topic.	Ideas are unclear and the speaker frequently loses focus on the topic.
Pronunciation	Pronounces words clearly and accurately, with minimal mispronunciation.	Pronounces words clearly, with occasional mispronunciation.	Pronounces words with some difficulty, but remains understandable.	Pronounces words with significant difficulty, making it hard to understand.
Vocabulary	Uses a wide range of relevant vocabulary and phrases naturally.	Uses a variety of relevant vocabulary and phrases.	Uses basic vocabulary and phrases.	Uses limited and repetitive vocabulary.
Grammar	Uses a variety of grammatical structures accurately and effectively.	Uses a variety of grammatical structures accurately.	Uses basic grammatical structures accurately.	Uses simple grammatical structures with frequent errors.

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Prelim Period

Week 1-4

WEEK 1

INTRODUCTION TO DEBATE GLOBALIZATION

Overview

This debate activity is designed to help high-achieving students explore and analyze different perspectives of globalization through structured arguments and discussions. Students will articulate their understanding of globalization, assess globalizing skills, and improve their communication abilities. The activity aligns with the outcome-based teaching and learning (OBT&L) and supports the measurement of students' communication and critical global citizens.

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Objectives

By the end of the debate, 75% of the students should be able to:

1. **Articulate Understanding of Globalization:** Present and defend at least three different interpretations of globalization through structured arguments.
2. **Economic and Cultural Impact:** Identify, describe, and discuss the economic and cultural impacts between various two-point definitions of globalization.
3. **Construct Logical Arguments:** Demonstrate improved ability to construct logical reasoning that supports views, and communicate effectively and formally during a debate.

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

1. **Group Formation:** Divide the class into four groups, each representing different perspectives of globalization (e.g., economic globalization, cultural globalization, political globalization, and social globalization).
2. **Research and Preparation:**
 - Provide each group with resources, including articles, expert interviews, and videos related to globalization.
 - Allow time for groups to research, discuss, and formulate their arguments and counterarguments.

DEBATE

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Debate Format

Opening Statements

- Each group presents their initial arguments (3-4 minutes per group)
- Focus on defining their conception of globalization and presenting key points

Rebuttal

- Each group responds to the opposing groups arguments (2-3 minutes per group)
- Address specific points raised by the opposition and present counter arguments

Open Floor

- Group members in a moderated discussion, using general cards challenging each other's points (10-15 minutes)
- Encourage active participation and active engagement with the opposing view

Closing Statements

- Each group will have 1-2 minutes to present their final points (2-3 minutes per group)
- Summarize their main arguments and address any remaining counter points

DEBATE

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Assessment Criteria

Content (30 points)

- Ability to cite relevance of the information presented
- Depth of understanding of the different conceptions of globalization

Argumentation (30 points)

- Strength and relevance of arguments and counterarguments
- Ability to respond to arguments with evidence and logical reasoning

Delivery (20 points)

- Clarity, confidence and persuasiveness of speech
- Effective use of language and communication techniques

Engagement (20 points)

- Active participation, respectful responses to arguments and challenges
- The presentation of critical thinking and analytical skills

DEBATE

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Feedback and Reflection

Constructive Feedback:

- Provide each group with feedback on their performance, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement
- Follow-up conversation, give constructive feedback and suggestions

Self-reflection:

- Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and interesting
- Have students discuss what they learned about globalization and their own communication skills

Example Topics

- Is economic globalization a necessary global action for a better world?**
- Is cultural globalization a good or bad globalization for the world?**
- Is fair trade globalization a better globalization for the world?**

DEBATE

WEEK 2-3

THE STRUCTURES OF GLOBALIZATION

Start of Discussion

Overview

The group discussion activity is designed to help fourth-year students explore the structures of globalization, including the global economy, global migration, global financial system, and global governance. Through collaborative discussions, students will enhance their understanding of these concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. The activity begins with the instructor leading a reading and writing plan (RWTP) that supports the development of product communication and informed global citizens.

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Objectives

By the end of the group discussion, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Define Economic Globalization:** Clearly explain the concept of economic globalization and its key components
- Analyze Issues and Institutions:** Identify and analyze the issues that influence economic globalization and the institutions that govern communication systems
- Discuss the Role of the United Nations:** Describe the role and functions of the United Nations in global communication

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

Group Formation: Divide the class into small groups (7-8 students per group)

Materials: Provide each group with materials, including articles, digital cards, and a case study. Distribute the assignment cards and allow time for you to answer questions and discuss the topic.

Discussion Format

- Individual Read:** Give groups 10-15 minutes to read their assigned articles
- Group Discussion:** Give groups 10-15 minutes to discuss, explore the topics in their assigned materials, and prepare a 2-3 minute presentation
- Individual and Presentation:** Each group will have 2-3 minutes to discuss and present their findings to the class (3-4 minutes per group)

GROUP DISCUSSION

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Assessment Criteria

- Content (30 points):** Accuracy and relevance of the information presented, depth of understanding of the structures of globalization
- Engagement (30 points):** Active participation and ability to contribute to the discussion, demonstration of critical thinking and analytical skills
- Communication (20 points):** Clarity, confidence, and persuasiveness of speech, effective use of language and communication techniques

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide each group with feedback on their performance, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Follow-up conversation, give constructive feedback and suggestions
- Self-reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and interesting. Have students discuss what they learned about the structures of globalization and their own communication skills

Example Discussions

- The Global Economy:** Discuss the role of institutions and agencies of economic globalization
- Global Migration:** Explore the processes of global migration and its impact on the world
- Global Governance:** Discuss the role and functions of the United Nations and other global governance institutions

GROUP DISCUSSION

WEEK 4-5

A WORLD OF REGIONS

Role Playing

Overview

The role playing activity is designed to help fourth-year students explore the concepts of the World Bank and World Trade Organization (WTO) through role playing scenarios. Students will address the understanding of these topics, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. The activity begins with the instructor leading a reading and writing plan (RWTP) that supports the development of product communication and informed global citizens.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

Objectives

By the end of the role playing activity, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Explain the Global North and Global South:** Discuss the role and functions of the Global North and Global South
- Analyze Regional Integration:** Identify the factors that lead to greater integration of Asia, Europe, and the Americas
- Identify the Role of the World Bank and WTO:** Discuss the role and functions of the World Bank and WTO

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

- Group Formation:** Divide the class into small groups (7-8 students per group)
- Assign Roles:** Assign each group a specific role or scenario related to the World Bank and WTO
- Individual and Presentation:** Each group will have 2-3 minutes to discuss and present their findings to the class (3-4 minutes per group)

ROLE PLAYING

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Role Playing Format

- Introduction:** Each group will have 10-15 minutes to read their assigned materials and prepare a 2-3 minute presentation
- Role Playing Scenarios:** Provide groups with role playing scenarios, assign their roles and materials, and allow 10-15 minutes for role playing
- Individual and Presentation:** After the role playing, each group will have 2-3 minutes to discuss and present their findings to the class (3-4 minutes per group)

Assessment Criteria

- Content (30 points):** Accuracy and relevance of the information presented, depth of understanding of the World Bank and WTO
- Engagement (30 points):** Active participation and ability to contribute to the discussion, demonstration of critical thinking and analytical skills
- Communication (20 points):** Clarity, confidence, and persuasiveness of speech, effective use of language and communication techniques

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide each group with feedback on their performance, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Follow-up conversation, give constructive feedback and suggestions
- Self-reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and interesting. Have students discuss what they learned about the World Bank and WTO and their own communication skills

ROLE PLAYING

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ROLE PLAYING

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide each group with feedback on their performance, highlighting strength to build upon for the future event. Focus on content, engagement, and communication.
- Reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and rewarding. Have students write a brief reflection on what they learned about the world, their role, and their own communication skills.

Example Scenarios

- Global North vs. Global South:** How does a Global North nation respond to a global health crisis from the Global South? Or, how does a Global South nation respond to a global health crisis from the Global North?
- Religion and Globalization:** How does a nation of a different religious background respond to globalization? How does a nation of a different religious background respond to globalization?
- Religion and Globalization:** How does a nation of a different religious background respond to globalization? How does a nation of a different religious background respond to globalization?

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Midterm

Week 7-11

WEEK 7-8

A WORLD OF IDEAS

Simulation

Overview

This simulation activity is designed to help fourth-year nursing students explore the dynamics between global cultures, media, and the globalization of religion. Through role playing, scenario, students will enhance their understanding of these topics, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. This activity aligns with the outcomes-based learning and teaching plan (OTLTP) and supports the development of professed competencies and intended general education.

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SIMULATION

Objectives

By the end of the simulation activity, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Analyze Media's Role in Global Integration:** Identify how different forms of media create and manipulate representations of global integration.
- Recognize How Globalization Affects Religious Expression Worldwide:** Discuss how globalization affects religious expression in different parts of the world.
- Examine the Relationship Between Media and Cultural Dynamics:** Analyze the relationship between media and the globalization of local and global cultures.

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

- Group Formation:** Divide the class into small groups (3-5 members) and assign each group a specific media organization, cultural context, or religious expression.
- Assign Roles:** Assign each group a specific role in the simulation related to global integration, religious expression, or cultural dynamics. Assign roles to each group member.
- Research:** Provide each group with resources, including articles, video, and news, and assign them to research and prepare their positions.

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SIMULATION

Simulation Format

- Media Conference Setup:** Arrange the classroom to simulate a media conference setting, with a panel of media representatives and an audience of cultural analysts and religious leaders.
- Opening Statements:** Each group presents their initial statements, outlining their perspectives on the influence of global media (3-5 minutes per group).
- Panel Discussion:** The audience engages in a panel discussion, asking questions and challenges from the audience (15-20 minutes). Encourage active participation and critical engagement with the topics.
- Audience Inquiry:** The audience (cultural analysts and religious leaders) asks questions and provides feedback on the panel's statements (10-15 minutes).
- Closing Statements:** Each group summarizes their key points and final arguments (2-3 minutes per group).

Assessment Criteria

- Content (10 points):** Accuracy and relevance of the information presented, depth of understanding of global media's role in culture and religion.
- Engagement (5 points):** Active participation and ability to respond to challenges, demonstration of critical thinking and analytical skills.
- Communication (5 points):** Clarity, confidence, and effectiveness of communication, ability to articulate ideas and respond to questions.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

SIMULATION

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide each group with feedback on their performance, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Focus on content, engagement, and communication.
- Reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and rewarding. Have students write a brief reflection on what they learned about global media's influence and their own communication skills.

Example Simulation

- Media's Role in Global Integration:** Discuss a news outlet's coverage of a global health crisis and its impact on global public health integration, addressing issues such as cultural differences, language barriers, and access to healthcare.
- Globalization of Religion:** Discuss a media organization's coverage of religious practices and beliefs, addressing both positive and negative effects.
- Media and Cultural Dynamics:** Discuss a media organization's coverage of religious practices and beliefs, addressing both positive and negative effects.

WEEK 9-11

GLOBAL POPULATION AND MOBILITY

Socratic Seminar

Overview

This Socratic seminar activity is designed to help fourth-year nursing students explore the topics of global population, mobility, global health, immigration, and migration. Through guided discussions, students will enhance their understanding of these concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. This activity aligns with the outcomes-based learning and teaching plan (OTLTP) and supports the development of professed competencies and intended general education.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

SOCRATIC SEMINAR

Objectives

By the end of the Socratic seminar, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Identify Attributes of Global Cities:** Describe the characteristics of global cities and their roles in driving globalization.
- Analyze Global Demographic Trends:** Discuss the trends and issues in global demographics, including population growth, aging, and migration.
- Reflect on Global Migration:** Reflect on the experiences of migrants and the impact of global migration on societies.

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

- Group Formation:** Arrange the class into small groups to facilitate open discussion. Assign roles to each group member in the seminar, including facilitator and note-taker.
- Assign Reading:** Provide students with articles, news articles, and relevant statistics on global cities, demographics, and migration. Assign roles to each group member in the seminar, including facilitator and note-taker.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

SOCRATIC SEMINAR

Socratic Seminar

Socratic Seminar

- Opening Question:** Start the seminar with an open-ended question related to the topic, such as "What are the driving forces behind the globalization of a global city?" or "How does global migration impact societies?"
- Facilitated Discussion:** Facilitate the discussion by asking follow-up questions, encouraging students to relate back to the topic. Examples include "What factors contribute to the development of global cities?" and "What are the challenges faced by migrants in different parts of the world?"
- Student Participation:** Encourage all students to participate, share their insights, and respond to each other's points. Ensure that the discussion remains respectful and focused on the topic.
- Closing Reflection:** Conclude the seminar with a reflective question, such as "How can we address the challenges of global migration or better handle global cities in shaping the future of globalization?"

Assessment Criteria

- Content (10 points):** Accuracy and relevance of the information presented, depth of understanding of global population and mobility.
- Engagement (5 points):** Active participation and ability to contribute to the discussion, demonstration of critical thinking and analytical skills.
- Communication (5 points):** Clarity, confidence, and effectiveness of communication, ability to articulate ideas and respond to questions.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

SOCRATIC SEMINAR

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide students with feedback on their participation, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Focus on content, engagement, and construction.
- Reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and rewarding. Have students write a brief entry on what they learned about global participation and mobility and how they can contribute to it.

Example Seminar Questions

- Global Cities:** What are the defining characteristics of a global city, and how do they differ from traditional cities?
- Global Connectivity:** What are the key drivers of global connectivity, and how do they impact society?
- Global Migration:** What are the implications of global population mobility, and how can we address the challenges it presents?

THE WORD OF WORLDS

Final Period

Week 13-17

WEEK 13-15

TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE WORLD

Overview

The final three weeks are designed to help teachers and students explore the concept of sustainable urban forms, global connectivity, and global citizenship. Through individual, paired, and group activities, students will enhance their understanding of these topics, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. The weekly "Word of the Week" (WOW) activity and weekly "Final Period" will support the development of practical communication and critical thinking skills.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

THINK-PAIR-SHARE

Objectives

By the end of the first four weeks, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Define Sustainable Development:** Explain the concept of sustainable development in a practical sense.
- Present the Concept of Global Food Security:** Analyze the issues and challenges of global food security and propose concrete solutions.
- Reflect on Global Citizenship:** Evaluate the implications of global citizenship and its role in addressing global challenges.

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

- Individual Reflection:** Provide students with writing materials and facilitate an individual reflection activity. Encourage them to think and reflect on the topic independently.

Think Phase

- Individual Reflection:** Provide students with writing materials and facilitate an individual reflection activity. Encourage them to think and reflect on the topic independently.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

THINK-PAIR-SHARE

Pair Phase

- Pair Formation:** Divide the class into pairs. Each pair will discuss their individual reflections and share their insights with each other.
- Discussion Questions:** Provide each pair with guiding questions to facilitate their discussions. Example questions: How can we improve the environment for a better future? What role do we have in addressing global food security?

Share Phase

- Group Sharing:** After the paired discussions, bring the class together for group sharing. Each pair will present their insights and thoughts to the class.
- Class Discussion:** Facilitate a class discussion based on the paired discussions. Encourage students to ask questions, provide feedback, and engage in a collaborative dialogue.

Assessment and Criteria

- Content (10 points):** Assess the depth of the student's understanding, clarity of explanation, and quality of reasoning.
- Engagement (10 points):** Assess participation and ability to contribute to the class discussion.
- Communication (10 points):** Assess articulation, and effectiveness of communication skills in articulating ideas and responding to questions.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

THINK-PAIR-SHARE

Feedback and Reflection

- Constructive Feedback:** Provide students with feedback on their participation, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. Focus on content, engagement, and construction.
- Reflection:** Encourage students to reflect on their learning experience and discuss what they found challenging and rewarding. Have students write a brief reflection on what they learned about sustainable development, global food security, and global citizenship.

Example of Think-Pair-Share Questions

- Sustainable Development:** What is sustainable development, and why is it important for a global world?
- Global Food Security:** What are the key challenges of global food security, and how can they be addressed?
- Global Citizenship:** What are the implications of a global citizen, and how can global citizenship contribute to addressing global challenges?

WEEK 16-17

GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP

Roundtable Discussion

Overview

The final two weeks of the activity are designed to help teachers and students explore the concept of global citizenship and its implications for addressing global challenges. Through individual discussions, students will enhance their understanding of global citizenship, develop critical thinking skills, and improve their ability to communicate effectively. The weekly "Word of the Week" (WOW) activity and weekly "Roundtable Discussion" will support the development of practical communication and critical thinking skills.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

ROUNDTABLE DISCUSSION

Objectives

By the end of the roundtable discussion, 75% of the students should be able to:

- Define Global Citizenship:** Explain the concept of global citizenship and its implications in a practical sense.
- Discuss Global Challenges:** Identify and discuss key global challenges and the role of global citizens in addressing these issues.
- Reflect on Personal Commitment:** Reflect on their own role and responsibilities as global citizens and how they can contribute to global solutions.

Instructions and Procedures

Preparation

- Group Formation:** Divide the class into small groups of 4-6 students and assign them to specific discussion topics.
- Assign Roles:** Assign each group member a specific role to facilitate the discussion, such as facilitator, note-taker, time-keeper, and reporter.
- Background:** Provide each group with background information on the topic and related resources on their assigned topic. Allow time for groups to research and prepare their discussion points.

THE WORD OF WORLDS

ROUNDTABLE DISCUSSION

Discussion Format

- Opening Statements:** Each group presents a 3-5 minute opening and has points on their assigned topic (3-5 minutes per group).
- Roundtable Discussion:** Through engage in a roundtable discussion, sharing their insights and responding to questions from other groups (15-20 minutes). Encourage active participation and a strong engagement with the topic.
- Summary and Reflection:** Each group summarizes their discussion, reflects on the key points and insights gained (10 minutes per group).

Assessment Criteria

- Content (10 points):** Assess the depth of the student's understanding, clarity of explanation, and quality of reasoning.
- Engagement (10 points):** Assess participation and ability to contribute to the discussion.
- Communication (10 points):** Assess articulation, and effectiveness of communication skills in articulating ideas and responding to questions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that this study was conducted in full adherence to established ethical standards. Prior to the commencement of data collection, the research underwent review and approval by the institution's Data Protection Department, and a formal Data Privacy Notice was submitted to ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after they were thoroughly briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights as respondents. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without any academic or personal repercussions. The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were strictly maintained, with all data securely stored and accessible only to the researcher and authorized personnel. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process, and no physical, emotional, or academic harm was inflicted. The researcher declares that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and originality of content, and all findings were interpreted objectively and without bias. The results of this study were used solely for academic and research purposes. For full transparency, the researcher acknowledges the use of artificial intelligence in supporting the development of this manuscript, while ensuring that all analyses, interpretations, and conclusions were independently formulated.

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